

THROUGH-THE-THICKNESS TENSILE IMPACT FRACTURE OF
THERMOSETTING AND THERMOPLASTIC POLYMER COMPOSITE PLATES

Nobuo Takeda, Haruo Komatsu and Kiyoshi Takahashi
Research Institute for Applied Mechanics,
Kyushu University,
Kasuga-City, Fukuoka 816,
Japan

ABSTRACT

So-called spall fractures, through-the-thickness tensile impact fractures in simple uniaxial strain were examined for typical glass fiber reinforced thermosetting and thermoplastic polymer composite plates. An exploding foil technique was used to accelerate thin flyer plates towards composite plates to generate spall fractures. For thermosetting polyester composites, different fiber surface treatments were applied to study the effects of interfacial strengths on the impact fracture threshold conditions and the spall mechanism. The static interfacial strength could be correlated with the threshold condition for the spall fracture initiation, but not with that for the complete separation fracture. Brittle debonding between fibers and resin was a main spall fracture mechanism. For thermoplastic polypropylene composites, on the other hand, plastic deformation played an important role in spall fractures to absorb considerable impact energy. Ellipse-shape spall fractures were observed in accordance with the fiber orientation of short fibers.

INTRODUCTION

The impact properties of composites have been often studied through conventional or instrumented Charpy and Izod impact tests. Test results, however, cannot provide any fundamental impact material properties which are directly applied to the design of real-size composite structures. As a consequence, the needs for simple and reliable impact test methods are rapidly increasing for composites where specimens experience only a simple dynamic stress or strain state.

Composites are often used as thin laminates and subjected to through-the-thickness impact loads. A thin flyer plate technique can be utilized to study the tensile impact fracture behavior of composite laminates in

simple uniaxial impulsive strain in the thickness direction. An impact-induced compressive stress wave is reflected at a free surface as a tensile wave, which can produce through-the-thickness tensile fractures called spall fractures. Some previous studies on spall fractures in composites have been made by other investigators [1-3]. Few studies have been conducted, however, to investigate the spall fracture initiation mechanisms and their relationship with the spall fracture threshold conditions and the material properties.

In this paper, the threshold conditions for the spall fracture initiation and the complete separation fracture are determined as fundamental impact material properties for typical glass fiber reinforced thermosetting and thermoplastic polymer composite plates. The spall fracture mechanisms are also examined through the micrographs of specimen sections.

EXPERIMENT

A thin poly(methyl methacrylate)(PMMA) flyer plate was accelerated by explosion of a thin aluminum foil (Fig. 1) [4]. After an evacuated free run, the flyer plate struck the specimen plate with very little tilt. Time difference of contacts between the aluminum-coated flyer plate and two pairs of thin copper wires (velocity pins) was detected electrically to measure the impact speed of the flyer plate, V .

A uniaxial strain state can be achieved in the specimen plate since

(a) Exploding foil assembly

(b) Specimen geometry

Figure 1. Experimental setup of a thin flyer plate technique by means of foil explosion.

the impact is planar. When an impact-induced compressive wave encounters a free surface of the flyer plate or the specimen, a reflected rarefaction wave is generated. At the time and place where two rarefaction waves meet, a tensile stress pulse is formed. So-called spall fractures occur inside the specimen if the tensile stress amplitude σ and the stress duration t_d are sufficiently large. If one-dimensional linear elastic stress wave propagation and rectangular waveforms are assumed, the following equations are obtained:

$$\sigma = V \cdot Z_f \cdot Z_s / (Z_f + Z_s), \quad t_d = 2t_f / c_f \quad (1)$$

where Z_f and Z_s are mechanical impedances of the flyer and the specimen, respectively, and t_f and c_f are the thickness and the longitudinal wave-speed of the flyer, respectively. The above assumption is reasonably valid at the relatively low stress amplitude reported here. Different conditions can be achieved by changing the speed and the thickness of the flyer plate. In the present study, the stress duration t_d was fixed at $0.77 \mu\text{s}$ since $t_f = 1 \text{ mm}$ and $c_f = 2,600 \text{ m/s}$. The stress amplitude σ or the flyer impact speed V was changed to obtain the threshold conditions for the spall fracture initiation and the complete separation fracture.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thermosetting Polymer Composites

Table 1 shows tested glass fiber reinforced polyester (thermosetting polymer) composites and one neat resin. Effects of reinforcement types were examined through materials A(unidirectional), B(plain-woven) and C (satin-woven). Effects of fiber surface treatments, on the other hand, were demonstrated by comparing materials C(acryl silane), D(chrome) and E(no surface treatment). Short-beam shear and bending strengths are different for different types of fiber surface treatment. Void volume contents were estimated at less than 0.5 % for materials B, C and D, 1 % for material A, and 2 - 3 % for material E. Visual examination reveals the spall fracture initiation and the complete separation fracture in the specimen. All the test results are summarized in Fig. 2. Regardless of some scatter in test data, the threshold impact speeds for the spall fracture initiation and for the complete separation fracture, V_{sp} and V_{cs} , respectively, can be determined as listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1
Glass fiber reinforced polyester composites and their properties

Material Symbol	A	B	C	D	E	F
Glass Fiber Reinforcement	Uni-directional	Loose Plain-Woven	8-Shaft Satin-Woven	8-Shaft Satin-Woven	8-Shaft Satin-Woven	None
Fiber Surface Treatment	Acryl Silane	Acryl Silane	Acryl Silane	Chrome	None	None
Thickness (mm)	2.97	3.30	2.18	2.14	2.32	2.04
Fiber [Void] Volume Content $V_f [V_v]$ (%)	51.3 [1.0]	44.3 [<0.5]	43.3 [<0.5]	43.2 [<0.5]	41.0 [2-3]	0 [n.a.]
3-Pt Bending Strength (MPa)	n.a.	n.a.	556	446	374	n.a.
Short Beam Shear Strength (MPa)	n.a.	n.a.	58.2	50.2	30.0	n.a.
Spall Speed, V_{sp} (Threshold) (m/s)	70	70	60	60	45	100-120
Separation Speed, V_{cs} (Threshold) (m/s)	n.a.	(170)	180	145	205	n.a.

a) Span : 50 mm, b) Span : 10 mm, c) n.a. = not available.

For the value of V_{sp} , the following conclusions can be drawn from the experimental results:

- [1] The V_{sp} for a neat resin (material F) is much higher than that for composites: This is due to stress concentrations in relatively soft resin reinforced by stiff fibers. The V_{sp} for material C, for example, is 60 m/s which corresponds to the stress amplitude of about 100 MPa, while 110 m/s (180 MPa) for the neat resin.
- [2] The effects of glass fiber reinforcement types on the V_{sp} value are small for tested composites: Different reinforcement types were used for materials A, B and C with the same fiber surface treatment. The values of V_{sp} for materials A and B are a little higher than that for material C, presumably because of the large thickness which induces higher attenuation of the stress wave. Therefore, similar values of V_{sp} are expected for materials A, B and C with the same thickness.

Figure 2. Spall fracture and complete separation in five polyester composite and one neat resin plates. The threshold impact speeds V_{sp} and V_{cs} can be determined.

[3] The effects of fiber-matrix interfacial strengths on the V_{sp} value are clearly observed: Different fiber surface treatments were applied to the same type of glass fabric in materials C, D and E. The effect of the fiber surface treatment is most pronounced in material E which has a much smaller V_{sp} value than materials C and D. Weak bonding between fibers and matrix resin causes a lower spall threshold speed. The values of V_{sp} are similar for materials C and D even though the fiber surface treatments are different.

For the value of V_{cs} , material C has a higher V_{cs} value than material D. It should be noted that material E has a much larger V_{cs} value than materials C and D. This is probably due to the voids in the specimen. Material E possesses a larger void content and a large amount of impact energy may be dissipated due to crack blunting caused by voids.

The sections of the impacted specimens were observed microscopically to study the mechanisms of the spall fracture initiation. For all the tested materials, planar spall fractures were observed at the distance of 1 to 1.7 mm below the specimen free surface. The distance increases with

increasing the specimen thickness. Scanning electron micrographs (Fig. 3) reveal that a spall crack tends to propagate at or near the fiber-resin interface. The crack avoids so-called resin-rich regions, but usually propagates through fiber-dense regions. Similar observations have been conducted with transverse cracks in cross-ply glass fiber composite laminates impacted by projectiles [5]. Since the strain concentration in a direction perpendicular to fibers increases as the interfiber spacing decreases [6], the spall crack is likely to propagate particularly in regions where adjacent fibers are touching. As a consequence, the interfacial bonding strength becomes an important factor to determine the threshold impact speed for the spall fracture initiation.

(a) Material A, $V = 147.4$ m/s

(b) Material B, $V = 87.0$ m/s

Figure 3. Micrographs of spalled specimen sections of polyester composite plates. It should be noted that the spall crack tends to propagate at or near the fiber-resin interface.

Thermoplastic Polymer Composites

The above micrographs indicate that the polyester resin fractures in a brittle manner with little elongation. A high-elongation resin may be useful to prevent the early spall fracture. Thermoplastic polymers have much potential in this respect. Injection-molded short glass fiber reinforced polypropylene composite plates (2.75–2.80 mm thick, $V_f = 20$ and 40 %) were tested in a similar manner. The diameter and the average length of silane-treated fibers were approximately 13 and 100 μm , respectively. Specimens (15 mm x 50 mm) were cut from a plate as shown in Fig. 4(a).

Summary of results is shown in Fig. 5. The V_{sp} values are 98 and 108 m/s for $V_f = 20$ and 40 %, respectively. These values are larger than

those for thermosetting polyester composites. The V_{sp} value is larger for a larger V_f value, which is different from the result for polyester based composites. This is presumably due to the following two reasons:

(a) Injection-molded plate and specimens (b) Ellipse-shape spall fracture

Figure 4. Injection-molded short fiber reinforced polypropylene composite plates and spall shapes.

Figure 5. Spall fracture in polypropylene composite plates.

(a) $V_f = 20\%$, $V = 132$ m/s

(b) $V_f = 40\%$, $V = 163$ m/s

Figure 6. Micrographs of spalled specimen sections of polypropylene composite plates. Arrows indicate severe plastic deformation.

- [1] As the V_f increases, dispersion and attenuation of stress waves increases and the stress amplitude at the spall location decreases.
- [2] As the V_f increases, the plastic deformation of the resin is more constrained between fibers.

Sections of spalled specimens are shown in Fig. 6. The spall fracture consists of a few layers of fractures probably due to the short fiber reinforcement. Considerable plastic deformation can be observed along the spall crack and much impact energy was dissipated through the plastic deformation. Thus, the thermoplastic resin introduces much plastic deformation during the spall fracture, which reduces the stress concentration and prevents the brittle fracture. As a result, spall fracture mechanisms are quite different for thermosetting and thermoplastic polymer composites.

Injection-molded plates have different fiber orientations at different regions of molding. Specimens A, B, B' and C (Fig. 4(a)) were tested to study this effect. Sections of the same spalled specimen in both x and y directions are shown in Fig. 7 for the specimen A. Fibers are mainly oriented in the y direction near front and back surfaces, but in the x direction inside the specimen where the spall fracture occurs. These fiber orientations are more pronounced for the specimens B, B' and C, and also for specimens with a higher V_f ($V_f = 40\%$). Effects of fiber orientations on the V_{sp} value were not observed during the study. However, the spall shape was affected by fiber orientations. Ellipse-

(a) x-section

(b) y-section

Figure 7. Sections of the same spalled specimen in both x and y directions.

shape spall fractures (Fig. 4(b)) are formed with the longitudinal axis normal to the direction of fiber orientation. The length ratio of the longitudinal and the transverse axes is found to increase as the degree of fiber orientation increases. Thus, spall shapes are closely related with fiber orientations. Stress concentration between fibers is different in the x and y directions, which is supposed to affect spall shapes. The detail is still under investigation.

CONCLUSIONS

Through-the-thickness tensile impact fractures (spall) were studied for glass fiber reinforced thermosetting polyester and thermoplastic polypropylene composite plates. The threshold impact speeds for the spall fracture initiation (V_{sp}) and the complete separation fracture (V_{CS}) were determined as fundamental impact material properties.

For continuous fiber/polyester composites, the following conclusions can be drawn for the value of V_{sp} :

- [1] The V_{sp} for a neat resin is much higher than that for composites.
- [2] The effects of fiber reinforcement types are small.
- [3] Interfacial shear strengths can be well correlated with the V_{sp} values.

The value of V_{CS} , however, cannot be correlated with the interfacial strengths alone. The void contents have to be also taken into account. Debonding between fibers and resin is a main spall fracture mechanism. The crack avoids resin-rich regions, but propagates through fiber-dense regions, particularly regions where adjacent fibers are touching and the high strain concentration exists. Thus, the spall crack tends to propagate at or near the fiber-resin interface. The interfacial strength is an important factor to determine the spall fracture threshold condition.

For short fiber/polypropylene composites, on the other hand, the V_{sp} value is larger for a larger V_f value. Considerable plastic deformation can be observed along the spall crack and much impact energy is dissipated through the plastic deformation, which reduces the stress concentration. Ellipse-shape spall fractures are formed. Spall shapes are closely related with fiber orientations of short fibers.

REFERENCES

1. Schuster, D.M. and Reed, R.P., Fracture behavior of shock-loaded boron-aluminum composite materials, J. Comp. Mater., 1969, 3, 562-76.
2. Cohen, L.J. and Berkowitz, H.M., Dynamic fracture of a quartz-phenolic composite under stress-wave loading in uniaxial strain, J. Franklin Inst., 1972, 293, 25-45.
3. Shen, L.T., Zhao, S.D., Bai, Y.L., Yang, D.G. and Chen, S.X., A study of spallation in phenolic-resin based woven roving glass fiber reinforced composite material, In Proc. 4th Int. Conf. Comp. Mater., ed. Hayashi, T., Kawata, K. and Umekawa, S., Japan Soc. Comp. Mater., Tokyo, 1982, pp. 887-93.
4. Takeda, N., Komatsu, H. and Takahashi, K., Spall fracture mechanisms of glass fiber composite laminates impacted by flyer plates, In Proc. 3rd Japan-US Conf. Comp. Mater., ed. Kawata, K., Umekawa, S. and Kobayashi, A., Japan Soc. Comp. Mater., Tokyo, 1986, pp. 85-92.
5. Takeda, N., Sierakowski, R.L. and Malvern, L.E., Microscopic observations of cross sections of impacted composite laminates, Comp. Tech. Rev., 1982, 4, 40-4.
6. Kies, J.A., Maximum strains in the resin of fiberglass composites, U.S. Naval Res. Lab. Report No. 5752, 1962.